

Nitrogen isotopes in the interstellar medium: a chemical journey across the Galaxy

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One of the most important tools to investigate the chemical history of our Galaxy and our own Solar System is to measure the isotopic fractionation of chemical elements. This is the process that distributes the less abundant stable isotopes of an element in different molecular species. The isotopic ratios are governed by two main processes: 1. local fractionation effects; 2. chemical evolution of the whole Galaxy due to stellar nucleosynthesis.

Figure 1: $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$ vs D/H ratios measured in comets, chondrites, hot spots in insoluble organic matter (IOM) of meteorites, Earth and the proto-Solar nebula (PSN).

Introduction

Pristine Solar System materials, like comets and carbonaceous chondrites in meteorites, present very different hydrogen and nitrogen isotopic ratios ($\text{D}/\text{H} \sim 10^{-4}$ and $^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N} = 50\text{--}200$, e.g., [1, 2, 3] and see Figure 1) with respect to those measured for the proto-Solar nebula (PSN), in which our Sun was born ($\text{D}/\text{H} \sim 2 \times 10^{-5}$ and $^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N} = 441$; [4, 5]). Star-forming regions also present a variety of isotopic ratios, with a lower enrichment of the heavier isotopes with respect to the one present in pristine Solar System materials (e.g., [6, 7, 8]; see Figure 2 for $^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N}$ ratios). Nowadays observations and theoretical works about hydrogen fractionation (D/H ratios) agree about the processes that enrich deuterium with respect to hydrogen during star-formation. These processes are related to the cold phases ($T < 20\text{ K}$) of star-forming regions, where the CO freeze-out on grain surfaces and, because of this, gas-phase molecules are enriched in deuterium thanks to the so-called isotopic-exchange reactions [9]. These reactions exchange one of the hydrogen of a molecule with a deuterium. However, similar reactions cannot explain nitrogen fractionation ($^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N}$ ratios). In fact, chemical models that only includes these reactions are not able to reproduce the spread of $^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N}$ ratios for the different molecules and

in the different physical conditions of the observed targets (e.g., [10, 11, 12].) This indicates that other physical and/or chemical processes are needed to explain the observed values.

Figure 2: $^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N}$ ratio derived for different molecules and towards different star-forming regions, as indicated in the legend. The horizontal yellow and red solid lines represent the PSN value of 441 and the terrestrial atmosphere (TA) value of 272, respectively. The green horizontal line denotes the average value measured in comets. Moreover, the pink area represents measurements in carbonaceous chondrites, where the lower ones are the so-called “hot spots”.

Today, there is growing evidence supporting the idea that our Sun was born in a stellar cluster including also massive stars, with masses higher than $8 M_{\odot}$ (e.g., [13]). For this reason, the study of the chemical content of massive star-forming regions can give us crucial information about the chemical heritage of our Solar System.

The role of Galactic chemical evolution

The isotopic ratios measured in interstellar molecular clouds not only depends on local chemical fractionation effects, but also on the chemical evolution of the whole galaxy due to stellar nucleosynthesis. In particular, the $^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N}$ elemental ratio is a good indicator of stellar nucleosynthesis since the two elements are not produced in the same way (e.g., [14]). In this context, we have studied N-fractionation towards a statistically significant sample of 87 massive star-forming regions located at galactocentric distances (D_{GC}) from 2 up to 12 kpc. We have derived the $^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N}$ ratios for HCN and HNC as a function of the galactocentric distance, and compared the results with Galactic chemical evolution (GCE) model predictions ([15, 16]; see Figure 3). These models predict a linear positive $^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N}$ ratio up to 8 kpc, and a flattening

trend for higher distances. This behavior is mainly due to the production of ^{15}N in nova outbursts [14, 17]. The results we have obtained shows an agreement between models and observations, confirming the importance of nova outbursts for the ^{15}N enrichment along the Galactic disc. Furthermore, we have found a local $^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N}$ ratio of ~ 375 , consistent with a local chemical evolution due to stellar nucleosynthesis. Thus, stellar nucleosynthesis processes can explain, on average, the observed $^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N}$ values, which are lower than the PSN value, but are not able to reproduce the different values from region to region, and from molecules to molecule.

Figure 3: $^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N}$ ratios for HNC as a function of the galactocentric distance (D_{GC}). The cyan solid line is the linear regression fit computed for the two data sets, the red parabola is the results from the parabolic analysis described in detail in [16], and the pink solid line represents the GCE model of [14].

Local chemical effects

To investigate more in detail the processes that could enrich ^{15}N in molecules during the star-formation process, we have studied high-angular resolution observations (3", i.e. ~ 6200 au) from the IRAM NOEMA interferometer of the massive protocluster IRAS 05358+3543 [18]. In particular, we have resolved for the first time the spatial distribution of the ^{15}N -isotopologues of N_2H^+ at core scales (about 0.03 pc, Figure 4). The spatial resolution of these observations is one order of magnitude higher than previous works, allowing to distinguish the emission of dense cores inside a more diffuse envelope in which they are embedded. The maps of $^{15}\text{NNH}^+$ and N^{15}NH^+ shows that the $^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N}$ ratio of N_2H^+ is lower in the inner denser cores (~ 100 – 200) with respect to the more diffuse gas (>250). This result highlights the importance of local effects, and in particular it demonstrates that isotope-selective photodissociation of N_2 should be

introduced in chemical models to explain ^{15}N -enrichment in star-forming regions (e.g., [18, 19, 20]).

Figure 4: First interferometric maps of the $J=1-0$ transition of $^{15}\text{NNH}^+$. The black contour levels are 3, 5 and 7 times the 1σ of the map ($0.72 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$). The blue contours correspond to the 5σ of the map, from which the $^{14}\text{N}/^{15}\text{N}$ ratios have been derived. The black and blue squares indicate the positions of the continuum sources and other N_2H^+ peak positions, respectively. The dashed circle represents the NOEMA field of view and the synthesized beam is the ellipse indicated in the lower left corner.

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